

Consumer Brand Preference Towards Cosmetics Goods in Ramanathapuram

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Abstract

Present study, is based on survey of brand preference of customer in Ramanathapuram. An attempt is made to determine the brand preference, awareness and factors influencing the responses of 100 respondents. Study concludes that brand preference of younger generation.

Keywords: Source of awareness, factors influence and preference of brand.

Introduction

At present Indian market is a complex one, so many brands are available for each item and the stress of selection rests with the present day consumer. In the way of all these study has been undertaken to analysis whether consumers are governed by habitual purchase and remain loyal to their brands of cosmetics many a time or repeated purchase are mistaken to be brand loyalty.

An important indicator of marketing is the success of an enterprise in the hands of number of its loyal customers. Customer's loyalty therefore is an important index to determine the competitive position of the firm. This is also used as the basis of segmenting the market and evolving the marketing strategy for each segment and also to encourage customer loyalty.

Organisation of the Paper

The whole paper is divided into 4 parts. After introduction of the theme, the second part describes the objectives and methodology of the study. Third part describes the results of the study where last part concludes some suggestions and future areas of intensive research.

Objective of Study

Objective of this study is to find out the brand loyalty pattern of the consumers.

1. To study the behaviour of consumers while purchasing cosmetics.
2. To measure the attitude of consumers towards the attributes of various brands.
3. To prove into the factors resulting in brand loyalty.

Period of Study

The field survey was carried out during the period from August 2018 to October 2018, to collect the primary data.

Limitations

The study was made only in Ramanathapuram, and the sample size has been restricted to 100 samples due to time constraints.

Methodology

The area of study is Ramanathapuram. The study is based on the primary data only. The questionnaire for collection of data was prepared in such a way that questions were simple and intelligible so as to enable the respondents to express their opinions freely and frankly.

Sampling

The sampling procedure used in this study was convenience sampling method. The sampling size was 100 respondents.

The statistical tools used to analyse the data in tune with the objectives of the study were,

1. Percentage analysis, 2. Chi-square analysis and 3. Garret's ranking technique

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Age Wise Classification

Sl.No.	Age (in years)	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	21-30	36	36
2	31-40	44	44
3	41-50	20	20
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 gives the age wise classification of the sample respondents, among 100 respondents selected for the study 36% belong to an aged group of 21-30 years and 44% of the respondents belong to an age group of 31-40 years, remaining 20% belongs to an age group of 41-50 years.

Table 2 Occupation Wise Classification

Sl.No.	Occupation	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Government employee's	28	28
2	Private employee's	26	26
3	Professional's	18	18
4	Business	15	15
5	Others	13	13
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 reveals that out of 100 respondents, 28% of respondents belong to government employees, 26% belong to private employee, the professional, and business people were 18% and 15% respectively and the remaining comes under others category.

Table 3 Sources of Information About Brand

Sl.No.	Sources of Information	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Television	42	42
2	Friends & Relatives	25	25
3	Salesman	16	16
4	Newspaper & Journals	7	7
5	Others	10	10
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 that 42 % of respondents got brand awareness through television, 25% of the respondents through friends and relatives, 16% of the respondents through salesman, 7% through newspaper, and others were 10% respectively.

Table 4 Classification According to Attributes Towards Soap

Sl.No.	Attitude towards Soap	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Skin Sensitivity	31	31
2	Fragrance	36	36
3	Price	23	23
4	Others	10	10
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 that 36% of the respondents those who used the soap must possess the attribute fragrance 31% of a respondents those who used skin sensitivity and remaining 33% of the respondents price and other reasons.

Table 5 Impact of Age and Choice of Cosmetics (Soap) Age (in years)

Sl.No.	Brand	21-30	31-40	41-50	Total
1	Life boy	8	10	4	22
2	Hamam	8	3	6	27
3	Nature power	12	7	2	21
4	Cinthol	4	9	5	18
5	Others	4	5	3	12
	Total	36	44	20	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 indicates that 27% of the respondents are using hamam, 22% of respondents are using life boy, 21% of respondent are using nature power and remaining 30% of the respondents are using cinthol and other soaps.

Table 6 Brand Preference and Age of the Customer

Sl.No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Skin sensitivity	32	32
2	Fragrance	29	29
3	Price	27	27
4	Others	12	12
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 that 32% of the respondent feel that they are skin sensitive in choosing a brand of cream followed by fragrance holding 29 percent and 27 and 12 percent of the respondent price and other reasons.

Table 7 Impact of Age and Choice of Customer (CREAM)

Sl.No.	Brand/Age	21-30	31-40	41-50	Total
1	Fair ever	12	10	3	25
2	Fair & lovely	11	16	2	29
3	Garnier	7	8	-	15
4	Ponds	4	6	2	12
5	Others	2	4	13	19
	Total	36	44	20	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 7 that 29 percent of respondents used for fair & lovely, 25 percent of respondents used for fair ever, 19 percent of respond used after brands, remain 12 and 115 percent of the respond used ponds and garnier respectively.

Table 8 Age of the Customer and Brand Preference

Age (In years)	1	2	3	4	5	Total
20-30	12	11	7	4	2	36
30-40	10	16	8	6	4	44
40-50	3	2	-	2	13	20
Total	25	29	15	12	19	100

The calculated value is 37.578 and tabulated value @5% significant level is 15.5. sine the table value is less than the calculated value. The hypothesis is accepted thus, it is concluded that there is no see significant relationship between age of the customer and brand preference.

Table 9 Factors Influence Brand Image

Sl.No.	Factors	1	2	3	4	5	Total Score	Rank
1	Price	17	16	18	32	17	284	III
2	Quality	53	24	8	6	9	406	I
3	Durability	12	28	20	22	18	290	II
4	Package	8	26	30	18	18	288	V
5	Brand image	10	6	24	22	38	218	V

Source: Primary Data

Table 9 that most of the respondents here assigned first rank to quality, second rank to durability third rank to price, fourth rank to package and fifth rank to brand image.

Suggestions

1. To improve the volume of sales, the quality must be perfect.
2. Advertisement can be increased in various media for the awareness of the customer.
3. The company should always be in a position to receive continuous feedback and suggestions from its customers.

Conclusion

Brand preference by consumers is an asset to every cosmetic many factors. It may be concluded that among the consumers of Ramanathapuram. Brand preference is more in the case of soaps and creams are more used by the younger generation.

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